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Dual-Inductive and Programmable Switching: A New Paradigm in Ionic Interface-Controlled Perovskite Memory

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ABSTRACT

While halide perovskite (HP) memristors exhibit significant potential for artificial neural networks, their reliance on stochastic filamentary switching severely compromises operational stability. Here, we demonstrate a fully programmable, forming-free HP memristor that overcomes this intrinsic stochasticity through precise ionic interface engineering. By employing 1,4-butanediammonium iodide (BDAl₂) as an ion-modulating layer, we construct a structurally rigid, cross-linked interfacial network strongly anchored to the 3D HP surface, forming the grain boundaries-modulated barrier switching. The robust ion-blocking barrier fundamentally suppresses random filamentary growth. Resistive switching (RS) is instead governed by dynamic interfacial barrier modulation, driven by the asymmetric accumulation of mobile ions that electrostatically modulates charge injection. Crucially, this stable non-filamentary mechanism enables highly reproducible, bidirectional dual-inductive responses, and distinct non-zero crossing behaviors. For the first time in an operational HP memristor, we successfully achieved these combined dynamic features. We precisely control programmable multi-level states governed by compliance current and operation velocity. This defect-engineered, interface-driven approach establishes a highly reliable and dynamically controllable paradigm for advanced neuromorphic computing and analog memory architectures.

1 | Introduction

The rapid advancement of data-intensive computing and multimodal artificial intelligence (AI) has accelerated the demands for neuromorphic computing paradigms. Memristive devices have been developed using a broad range of material systems, including metal oxides, silicon-based materials, carbon-based materials, biomaterials, and perovskites [1–4]. Among these various candidates, halide perovskites (HPs) are highly promising memristor candidates for artificial neural networks (ANNs) due to their mixed ionic-electronic nature, low-temperature solution processability, and exceptional compositional and interfacial tunability [5, 6]. Extensive compositional and interfacial engineering has demonstrated their low power consumption, high-energy efficiency, and multifunctionality [6, 7]. Their mixed ionic-

electronic conduction enables the emulation of synaptic plasticity and complex neuromorphic functionalities similar to the human brain system [8]. In HP memristors, resistive switching (RS) behaviors have been mainly interpreted within the frameworks of electrochemical metallization (ECM) and valence change mechanism (VCM), depending on whether switching is dominated by electrochemically active metal species or by the migration of ionic defects within the active layer. These mechanisms are manifested through either stochastic filamentary conduction or interfacial switching [9]. However, most conventional HP memristors primarily focus on stochastic RS for synaptic weight updates, without sufficient mechanistic discrimination or precise control over the underlying switching pathways. While they reproduce high-capacity memory features, they rely heavily on stochastic filamentary mechanisms [10, 11]. This random nature degrades

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operational stability and fails to capture the complex, time-dependent signal delays inherent to biological neural systems [12, 13].

Emulating advanced biological functions, such as spike-timing-dependent plasticity (STDP), requires precise control over these temporal delays [14]. In HP-based memristors, the dynamic interplay between ion migration and electronic transport causes anomalous inductive hysteresis in current–voltage (I – V) characteristics [15, 16]. While these inductive responses are essential for mimicking the biological functions, they remain notoriously unstable. The uncontrollability stems from the inherent difficulty in precisely controlling ionic motion, causing these behaviors to couple with random filamentary pathways [17]. Therefore, achieving a stable, fully programmable dual-inductive switching response without random filaments remains a critical challenge [18, 19].

Here, we present a new paradigm, which is programmable, dual-inductive switching in HP memristors via precise ionic interface engineering. To achieve this, we introduce 1,4-butanediammonium iodide (BDAI₂) to construct a robust, quasi-2D interfacial layer. Unlike conventional mono-ammonium spacers, the dual ammonium groups of BDAI₂ strongly anchor to the 3D pristine HP surface, forming a dense and cross-linked ion-blocking network [20–22]. We fundamentally suppress random filamentary growth using BDAI₂ treatment. Consequently, the highly stable, non-filamentary RS is governed by dynamic interfacial barrier modulation [23, 24]. For the first time in HP-based memristors, this precise interfacial control enables a unique bidirectional inductive response with distinct non-zero crossing behaviors. Crucially, harnessing this non-zero crossing enables the intrinsic storage of temporal history [25, 26]. This allows the device to emulate complex, time-dependent synaptic delays without requiring external complementary metal-oxide semiconductor (CMOS) timing circuits. Furthermore, these dual-inductive properties are fully programmable via external electrical stimuli. This non-filamentary, interface-controlled approach resolves the intrinsic stochasticity of HPs-based memristors. It demonstrates significant potential for contributing to the dynamic signal processing capabilities of artificial biological synapses.

2 | Results and Discussion

2.1 | Characteristics of Interface-Controlled HP Films

The device architecture of the dual-inductive and programmable switching memristor device is schematically illustrated in Figure 1a, consisting of an Ag/Butane-1,4-diammonium iodide (BDAI₂) interfacial layer/3D perovskite/PEDOT: PSS/ITO/glass structure. A key feature of this device design is the integration of a BDAI₂ post-treatment layer between the 3D perovskite and the top electrode. This layer serves as a functional ionic control layer to uniformly modulate ion-migration dynamics and prevent localized destructive breakdown. The well-defined vertically stacked layers of the fabricated device are further confirmed by the cross-sectional high resolution-field emission scanning microscopy (HR-FESEM) provided in Figure S1. The

cross-sectional SEM image clearly displays the uniform and dense growth of the 3D HP active layer on the glass/ITO/PEDOT:PSS substrate. Notably, the top BDAI₂ layer is observed as an ultrathin distribution, confirming its intended role as a localized surface passivation network without altering the bulk HP morphology.

To investigate the interfacial effect of the BDAI₂ layer on the perovskite film, we first examined the surface morphologies using a top-view HRFESEM at a magnification of $\times 50\,000$, as shown in Figure 1b,c. The pristine perovskite film without BDAI₂ treatment exhibits a typical polycrystalline structure with clearly defined grain boundaries in Figure 1b. In contrast, the BDAI₂-treated surface appears to be enhanced continuity and dense, characterized by preferential BDAI₂ accumulation anchoring along the grain boundaries in Figure 1c. To provide a more comprehensive view of the surface coverage and uniformity, higher-magnification SEM images ($\times 100\,000$) are provided in Figure S2a,b. Since these grain boundaries act as facilitated pathways for rapid ionic transport in halide perovskite-based electronic devices [27, 28], such morphological evolution suggests that the incorporation of BDAI₂ effectively passivates these defective channels. This widespread planarization ensures a more-controlled, delocalized ionic accumulation mechanism in the device, fundamentally suppressing random filamentary leakage [29, 30].

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) was further employed to observe the surface topography properties of the perovskite films Figure 1e,f. The BDAI₂ modification also results in a significant reduction in peak-to-valley height, leading to a highly continuous and planarized surface in 3D AFM images (Figure S3). The AFM images were conducted over a $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$ area through tapping mode, in which the root-mean-square (RMS) roughness (R_a) significantly decreased from 22.16 nm for the pristine film to 10.91 nm upon BDAI₂ treatment. This morphological refinement physically confirms that the BDAI₂ treatment promotes the growth of a more dense and smooth film, effectively passivating the grain boundaries that otherwise act as rough defect sites. This optimized, uniform ionic interface is a structural prerequisite for suppressing parasitic leakage currents and ensuring highly reproducible, non-filamentary switching in our memristive devices.

To investigate the effect of the BDAI₂ treatment on the crystal structural properties, X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were obtained as shown in Figure 1d and Table S1. Both the pristine and BDAI₂-treated films exhibit the characteristic diffraction patterns of the triple-cation perovskite [31, 32], confirming that the bulk crystal framework is well-preserved by the post-treatment of BDAI₂. Specifically, the primary peaks corresponding to the (110), (112), (202), (220), (310), (312), (224), and (314) crystal planes were observed at approximately 14.2° , 20.2° , 24.8° , 28.6° , 32.1° , 35.3° , 41.0° , and 43.5° , respectively, with negligible phase shifts between the two samples. Interestingly, following the BDAI₂ passivation, these primary peaks exhibit a minor shift of approximately 0.06° toward higher 2θ angles in Table S1. While this slight reduction in the d-spacing is close to the typical measurement margin of conventional XRD instruments, it suggests a subtle interfacial lattice relaxation rather than a macroscopic compressive strain. This localized structural modification originates from the partial substitution and robust chemical bonding of the large BDAI₂ organic cations at the surface and grain boundaries, confirming

FIGURE 1 | (a) Schematic illustration of perovskite memory device structure. The device consists of Ag/BDAI₂-treated surface layer/3D perovskite/PEDOT: PSS/ITO/glass. (b,c) Top-view field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) images of 3D perovskite without (b) and with (c) post-treatment of BDAI₂, showing that BDAI₂ layer preferentially covers grain boundaries and smooths the surface. (d) X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of both perovskite films without BDAI₂ treatment and with BDAI₂-treatment. (e,f) Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images of perovskite films without (e) and with (f) post-treatment of BDAI₂.

the successful formation of a tightly anchored, quasi-2D interfacial network [21, 33]. Additionally, the BDAI₂-treated film shows a weak yet distinct additional peak at $2\theta = 12.79^\circ$, which is absent in the pristine film. This peak is typically assigned to the (001) plane of PbI₂. Rather than indicating destructive bulk degradation, this minor emergence suggests a slight interfacial reconstruction during the BDAI₂ anchoring process [34]. Crucially, its extremely low intensity relative to the primary 3D HP peaks physically confirms that the bulk HP structure remains intact without destructive phase conversion after the ultra-thin nature of the surface treatment. This trace amount of a secondary phase at the grain boundaries or surface often acts as a beneficial synergetic buffer layer. It effectively passivates deep defects and further prevents catastrophic localized ionic filamentary pathways, which aligns perfectly with our highly stable non-filamentary switching model. This quasi-2D/3D interfacial architecture serves as a structurally rigid dynamic barrier modulation that homogeneously regulates ionic transport.

To further elucidate the chemical interactions and surface modifications induced by the BDAI₂ treatment onto the Cs_{0.05}(FA_{0.83}MA_{0.17})_{0.95}Pb(I_{0.83}Br_{0.13})₃ HP memristors, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were conducted [35]. Figure 2 presents the high-resolution spectra of the pristine and treated HP films, each in Figure 2a–f. Initially, the Pb 4f core-level spectra (Figure 2a,d) exhibit a negligible shift (~ 0.13 eV) in the binding energies of the Pb 4f_{7/2} and Pb 4f_{5/2} peaks following the surface treatment. The Pb 4f_{7/2} and Pb 4f_{5/2} peaks

shift slightly from 138.11 and 142.97 eV to 137.98 and 142.84 eV, respectively. This negligible shift of ~ 0.13 eV, which is near the instrument's resolution limit, implies that the Pb framework is not the primary interaction site, confirming that the bulk HP structural integrity remains intact without destructive phase conversion [36, 37].

Definitive evidence of the interfacial modification with BDAI₂ in the HP-memristor device is observed in the N 1s spectra (Figure 2b,e). The pristine HP film without any treatment onto the surface shows a single, symmetric peak (~ 400.38 eV, Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) 1.76 eV) corresponding to the bulk organic cations of FA and MA; however, the BDAI₂-treated HP film displays a clear deconvolution into two distinct chemical states. Along with the primary bulk N 1s peak, a newly formed surface-related N 1s peak emerges at a higher binding energy of 401.72 eV with FWHM 1.72 eV, maintaining the bulk N 1s peak at 400.10 eV with FWHM 1.77 eV [38]. This confirms the successful anchoring of the diammonium molecules (BDAI₂) onto the pristine HP surface. Furthermore, I 3d spectra (Figure 2c,f) also clearly identify the exact passivation target. After the treatment of BDAI₂ onto the pristine HP film, the I 3d_{5/2} and 3d_{3/2} peaks shift toward higher binding energies by a margin of 0.38 eV from 618.45 and 629.95 eV to 618.83 and 630.33 eV, respectively, while the FWHM remains entirely unchanged. This positive shift indicates a decrease in electron density around the iodide sites, verifying the formation of strong coordination and hydrogen bonding between the functional groups of the

FIGURE 2 | XPS spectra of (a–c) pristine control perovskite film (without BDAI₂ treatment) and (d–f) perovskite film treated with BDAI₂. High resolution spectra of (a,d) Pb 4f, (b,e) N 1s, and (c,f) I 3d.

BDAI₂ molecules and the undercoordinated surface halides. This selective interaction effectively passivates the halide vacancies while preserving the intrinsic structural uniformity of the halide lattice. Consequently, these spectral changes demonstrate that the BDAI₂ treatment onto the Cs_{0.05}(FA_{0.83}MA_{0.17})_{0.95}Pb(I_{0.83}Br_{0.13})₃ HP memristor makes a role in a highly selective and robust passivation layer through coordinate bonding with halide sites, stabilizing the interfacial structural integrity required for stable, non-filamentary memristive operations. Furthermore, the C 1s core-level spectra (Figure S4) support this molecular anchoring. The pristine film primarily exhibits typical peaks for carbon (C–C, ~284.8 eV), along with C–N and C=N bonds originating from the methylammonium (MA) and formamidinium (FA) cations of 3D bulk HP. Following the BDAI₂ treatment, the spectrum reveals an increase in the C–N peak intensity relative to the C=N peak. Since the 1,4-butanediammonium carbon backbone on the surface contains purely C–C and C–N bonds without any C=N characteristics, this enhancement of the C–N signal indicates the accumulation of the BDAI₂ aliphatic backbone on the HP surface [37, 39]. Unlike conventional mono-ammonium spacers, the diammonium nature of BDAI₂ allows both ends of the molecule (–NH₃⁺) to simultaneously coordinate with adjacent uncoordinated halide sites, physically bridging the grain boundaries. This establishes a robust ion-controlled network in the system that can inhibit the formation of localized filamentary pathways.

To physically verify that this chemical coordination effectively eliminates the surface defect states and prevents the formation of non-radiative recombination centers, we further investigated the optical properties using steady-state photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy (Figure S5) [39]. To ensure statistical reliability, the PL spectra were collected from three different positions on each film and averaged. The pristine HP film shows a relatively weak PL emission peak at 769.0 nm (FWHM = 48.1 nm), which is characteristic of the 3D HP phase. In contrast, the BDAI₂-treated HP film demonstrates a significant enhancement in PL intensity by approximately 13.05 times [34]. This tremendous increase in radiative recombination indicates a substantial reduction in non-radiative recombination centers, confirming that the BDAI₂ molecules effectively passivate surface traps. Moreover, the PL peak of the treated film exhibits a noticeable blue shift from 769.0 to 759.6 nm. Simultaneously, a distinct high-energy shoulder peak emerges at 670.1 nm for the BDAI₂-treated film, which is attributed to the excitonic emission of the ultra-thin quasi-2D interfacial network phase formed via interfacial reconstruction [40, 41]. Crucially, this highly surface-sensitive optical evidence perfectly complements the bulk-sensitive XRD analysis. While the absence of low-angle XRD peaks confirms that the 3D HP bulk framework remains intact, the high surface-sensitivity of PL reveals the formation of an ultra-thin low-dimensional interfacial layer. This apparent discrepancy between XRD and PL spectra results highlights that the BDAI₂-induced network is strictly

localized at the top surface rather than penetrating the bulk. This optimized quasi-2D/3D interface cooperatively eliminates the random deep defects that typically trigger localized breakdown. Consequently, this uniform trap passivation directly facilitates the area-distributed charge injection and dynamic interfacial barrier modulation governing our device, fundamentally rejecting random filamentary pathways.

2.2 | Dual-Inductive and Programmable Switching Characteristics of HP Films

Following the morphological and crystal structural characterizations as well as the surface chemical analysis and PL spectra, complete memristor devices were fabricated by depositing a silver (Ag) top electrode onto the perovskite films. To emphasize the role of the BDAI₂ treatment and PEDOT: PSS role, we first evaluated and compared the electrical performance of the pristine device without BDAI₂-treated memristor and BDAI₂-treated full device alongside the devices without the PEDOT: PSS layer with the same measurement condition in Figure S6. These devices were fabricated within the same batch, except for the BDAI₂ modification and PEDOT: PSS coating, and measured with the same conditions to ensure a fair comparison. Both pristine and treated devices were evaluated using a voltage range of ± 1 V at a scan speed of 10 V/s, with the compliance current (I_{cc}) fixed at 10^{-4} A. As shown in Figure S6a,b, devices fabricated without the PEDOT: PSS layer exhibited abrupt current jumps to the compliance limit, indicating the formation of localized conductive pathways due to the rough ITO surface, regardless of the BDAI₂ treatment. As shown in Figure S6c, the pristine device with the PEDOT: PSS layer exhibits unstable and stochastic switching behaviors with significant current fluctuations and stochastic noise during the repeated voltage sweeps. This highly irregular sweep is physically driven by unregulated ionic drift and the presence of high-density defects at the untreated interface of perovskite, which leads to parasitic leakage and unpredictable resistance states. In contrast, the post-treatment of BDAI₂ onto the pristine perovskite layer combined with the PEDOT: PSS layer, effectively transformed the switching characteristics into a highly stable and repeatable hysteresis loop in Figure S6d, providing the essential reliability for memristive applications.

Electrical performance of the resulting Ag/BDAI₂-treated surface layer/3D perovskite/PEDOT: PSS/ITO/glass architecture was subsequently evaluated through cyclic voltammetry with a semiconductor analyzer (B1500A) equipped with a probe station. As presented in Figure 3, the device exhibits robust and highly reproducible memristive switching properties in all various measurement conditions. In Figure 3a,b, the resistive switching (RS) characteristics of the BDAI₂-treated memristor were evaluated using cyclic voltage sweeps ($0\text{ V} \rightarrow +1\text{ V} \rightarrow 0\text{ V} \rightarrow -1\text{ V} \rightarrow 0\text{ V}$) over 100 cycles. The measurements were conducted at a scan rate of 10 V/s with I_{cc} of 10^{-5} A to ensure stable RS behavior. By strategically implementing the BDAI₂ surface treatment, we successfully realized a highly stable and reliable memristive system with precisely modulated ionic transport. A key observation is the presence of a bidirectional volatile switching, ‘dual-inductive switching’ effect [42, 43]. Unlike conventional bipolar RS, which undergoes a SET process from the high-resistance state (HRS)

to the low-resistance state (LRS) at one polarity and a RESET process at opposite polarity, the BDAI₂-treated memristor exhibits highly repeatable, gradual, and symmetric current flow at both polarities [44]. Rather than relying on static interfacial charge trapping, this unique dual-inductive behavior is enabled by the synergistic interface engineering of both the top and bottom boundaries. While the PEDOT: PSS layer physically stabilizes the bottom interface by preventing localized catastrophic breakdown, the BDAI₂ treatment effectively functions as a dynamic, bi-directional ion reservoir at the top interface. It allows mobile halide ions/vacancies to actively cross and modulate the interfacial energy barrier under both positive and negative external biases. While RS occurs symmetrically at both polarities, the hysteresis window is more prominently enhanced under negative bias. This observation suggests that the asymmetric barrier modulation, driven by interplay between the external electrical field and the internal field generated by accumulated ions at the interface, dictates the current response [42, 45, 46].

Notably, the BDAI₂-treated device demonstrates forming-free behavior from the first voltage sweep without any abrupt current jump. Consistent with the conduction mechanisms of typical interface-type RS devices [44, 47], this gradual I - V characteristic confirms that the resistive state is dictated by the continuous electrostatic modulation of the interfacial barrier rather than the formation of physical metallic filament. During the initial cycle, the device undergoes a stabilization process with a gradual increase in the high-resistance state (HRS) current level. This initial conditioning is physically attributed to the delocalized rearrangement of mobile ions and the steady filling of widespread interfacial traps under the applied electric field. Unlike the abrupt localized breakdown found in conventional filamentary devices, this spatially uniform electrostatic process subsequently leads to the highly reproducible and overlapping hysteresis loops observed in the remaining 100 cycles. The BDAI₂ surface treatment effectively passivates interface defects and suppresses ion-triggered parasitic leakage, providing the necessary reliability for stable non-filamentary switching memristors [48, 49].

The effect of scan rate on the RS behavior was further investigated in Figure 3c. As the scan rate decreased from 100 to 1 V/s, the hysteresis window (ON/OFF ratio) gradually broadened. This dynamic trend indicates that a sufficient timescale at low scan speed is required for effective ion migration and distributed dense accumulation at the rigid blocking interface. While slower sweeps allow ample time for ions to respond to the external electric field and sufficiently lower the injection barrier, faster sweeps surpass the ionic motion, thereby limiting the switching magnitude. These observations verify the intrinsic temporal dynamics of this memristor system, where the ionic flux is modulated by the sweep duration [7, 9, 14].

In typical memristive devices, the compliance current (I_{cc}) is employed to control the stability and dimensions of conductive pathways and the extent of ion accumulation and trap-filling processes, preventing irreversible device breakdown [50–52]. An optimal I_{cc} minimized switching variability and enhances operational stability. Consequently, rather than forming localized physical filaments, the degree of interfacial barrier modulation and delocalized distributed vacancies generation at the interface

FIGURE 3 | Current–voltage (I – V) characteristics of Ag/BDAI₂-treated surface layer/3D perovskite/PEDOT: PSS/ITO/glass devices. (a) I – V curve obtained from the first voltage sweep between ± 1 V at a scan rate of 10 V/s, with a compliance current of 10^{-5} A. (b) Successive I – V sweeps recorded during 100 consecutive cycles under the same measurement conditions, following the initial sweep shown in (a). (c) I – V responses at varying sweep rates (1, 10, 100 V/s), showing rate-dependent hysteresis behaviors measured within the identical ± 1 V sweep range. (d) I – V characteristics measured under different compliance currents from 10^{-5} A to 10^{-2} A at a scan rate of 10 V/s, highlighting the transition from zero-crossing to non-zero crossing behavior with increasing current threshold.

can be precisely tuned by the I_{cc} level. A higher current limit induces a denser accumulation of halide ions at the interface, whereas a lower limit restricts this ionic flux. The multi-level switching capabilities of the BDAI₂-treated memristor were further evaluated by sequentially increasing I_{cc} from 10^{-5} A to 10^{-2} A within a single device cell, as shown in Figure 3d. Remarkably, the device maintained exceptional operational stability by performing 100 continuous, reproducible cycles at each sequentially increased I_{cc} state (400 cycles in total) without any electrical breakdown. As the I_{cc} was sequentially increased, the LRS current exhibited a gradual rise up to 10^{-3} A, followed by a sharp escalation at 10^{-2} A. This non-linear current increment suggests a transition toward a highly conductive state, driven by the extensive filling of widespread shallow traps and the severe modulation of the interfacial barrier under higher current injection.

Noticeably, the I – V curves exhibit a conventional zero-crossing hysteresis at lower I_{cc} levels, which occurs because the restricted ionic flux allows for rapid ionic relaxation. However, at the maximum I_{cc} level, the curves shift to a prominent non-zero crossing behavior, where a significant residual current remains at zero bias [25, 26]. This phenomenon is direct evidence of

non-filamentary type switching, where a massive accumulation of ions at the BDAI₂ passivated interface generates a concentration gradient-driven diffusive ionic flux. When the voltage reaches zero, the delayed relaxation (reverse diffusion) of these ions temporarily maintains the lowered barrier state, producing the observed residual conduction current. Crucially, this highly dynamic, current-dependent variation strictly rules out the possibility of pure geometric capacitance. As established in fundamental memristor literatures [25, 53] and physical models [26, 54], the asymmetric residual current at 0 V is distinct evidence of a built-in potential driven by the steep concentration gradient of the accumulated halide ions/vacancies, fundamentally differing from simple static charge storage. Proving its exceptional interfacial robustness and multi-level switching reliability, the device successfully sustained these extreme non-zero crossing conditions without degradation. Ultimately, these distinctive switching behaviors, sensitive to both timescale of operation and current limit, demonstrate the fully programmable nature of this barrier modulation, positioning it as a highly reliable candidate for analog neuromorphic memory.

To further evaluate the operational versatility of the dual-inductive device, the device performance was investigated under

FIGURE 4 | Representative I - V characteristics of the BDAI₂-treated perovskite memory devices measured under different combinations of voltage sweep rates and compliance current. (a) Fast scan rate (100 V/s) with low compliance current (10^{-5} A). (b) Fast scan rate (100 V/s) with higher compliance current (10^{-4} A), showing a distinct non-zero crossing behavior. (c) Slow scan rate (1 V/s) with low compliance current (10^{-5} A). (d) Slow scan rate (1 V/s) with higher compliance current (10^{-4} A).

various combinations of voltage sweep rates and compliance currents (I_{cc}), as shown in Figure 4. Regardless of the conditions, the BDAI₂-treated memristor consistently maintained its characteristic hysteresis and programmable resistance states. In the fast scan regime presented in Figure 4a,b, a distinct dynamic stabilization process was observed during the initial cycles. The current level initially increased as the delocalized ionic accumulation was established and subsequently reached a stabilized state after a subtle reduction. This trend indicates that the ionic distribution undergoes a self-limiting optimization toward a steady-state interfacial barrier configuration.

A critical observation lies in the dynamic ionic response governed by the kinetic interplay between compliance current and scan rate. While the device exhibits near-zero-crossing behavior at relatively slower scan rates of 1 V/s and 10 V/s (Figures 4d and 3d), even under an I_{cc} of 10^{-4} A, Figure 4b demonstrates a prominent non-zero crossing behavior at a high-speed sweep of 100 V/s. This stems directly from the disparity in ionic relaxation time because slower sweeps allow accumulated ions to redistribute and reach a quasi-equilibrium state. In contrast, rapid transitions prevent the timely dissipation of high-density ions at the interface. Consequently, these residual ions sustain a significant ionic concentration gradient, which generates a diffusive ionic flux at zero bias. This physical process results in the observed non-zero crossing behavior [15, 25, 26].

Furthermore, a notable transition in switching hysteresis dominance occurred at slow scan rate of 1 V/s, as shown in Figure 4c,d. In these conditions, a more pronounced hysteresis window emerged in the positive bias region, contrasting with the negative-bias dominance observed during fast sweeps. This shift is attributed to the extended duration for ionic redistribution, allowing ions to migrate and modulate the injection barrier even under positive bias. The significantly reduced cycle-to-cycle variation at these slower rates indicates that providing sufficient time for ionic redistribution ensures a more deterministic and stable switching response. These observations in Figures 3 and 4 demonstrate that BDAI₂-mediated interface control provides a robust platform for reliable and time-programmable switching over a wide range of operational conditions.

To assess the practical feasibility and multilevel storage capability of the BDAI₂-modified HP memristor, a consecutive 4000-cycle endurance test was performed on single device cell using sequential DC bias sweeps in Figure 5. The compliance current (I_{cc}) was systematically modulated every 1000 cycles in the range between 10^{-3} A and 10^{-6} A to investigate the stability of the programmed multilevel states under varying ionic flux densities. All measurements were conducted at a scan rate of 10 V/s within a voltage range of ± 0.7 V, and the resistance states were extracted at a read voltage (V_{read}) of +0.15 V, where a well-defined window was observed.

FIGURE 5 | Multi-level switching reliability and statistical analysis. (a) Multi-level programmed endurance test over 4000 cycles with sequential current compliance (I_{cc}) from 10^{-3} A to 10^{-6} A. (b) Statistical resistance distribution for each I_{cc} level. The dashed arrows show the tendency of resistance level in HRS and LRS. (c) Cumulative probability plot of the ON/OFF ratio, demonstrating superior uniformity and the tendency of memory window.

As depicted in the continuous cyclability test in Figure 5a, the dual-inductive memristor device maintains remarkable operational integrity throughout the 4000-cycle stress test. Due to the complete absence of significant degradation or fluctuations, the device can operate stably and be reliably programmed into distinct resistance states. This behavior suggests the diammonium organic interlayer ($BDAI_2$) effectively suppresses the stochastic overgrowth of metallic or vacancy-based conductive pathways, facilitating a highly reproducible and reversible non-filamentary switching process. The resulting statistical resistance distributions for each I_{cc} level reveal a distinct evolution in the switching kinetics in Figure 5b. Following the arrow direction in the statistical data, the HRS value gradually increases as the compliance current value decreases from 10^{-3} A to 10^{-5} A, indicating the precise controlled modulation of the ionic migration and barrier height. Conversely, the LRS value shows minimal variability at higher compliance currents (10^{-3} A and 10^{-4} A), but increases remarkably as the I_{cc} is reduced to 10^{-5} A and 10^{-6} A. Correlating with the behaviors observed in Figures 3 and 4, the programmed memristor consistently exhibits the

characteristics linking the presence or absence of zero-crossing to the corresponding changes in the switching window gap.

The tight distribution of the ON/OFF ratio in Figure 5c further demonstrates the deterministic nature of the switching mechanisms. The exceptionally steep slope of the cumulative probability curve exhibits high uniformity with minimal inter-cycle fluctuations. In particular, the distribution at 10^{-5} A occupies the highest range of properties that do not overlap with other states, identifying it as the optimal operating threshold for high-density multilevel memory, which is why we measured our primary data acquisition under these conditions. These properties suggest that the RS is effectively regulated by spatially uniform interface dynamics, addressing the stochasticity issues frequently encountered in conventional HP memristors. This significantly mitigates the randomness that hinders the practical memristor application of HP. Ultimately, we confirm that the synergy between the $BDAI_2$ interface and precision current control enables a highly reliable multilevel memory platform suitable for sophisticated analog neuromorphic architectures.

FIGURE 6 | I-V characteristics of Au/BDAI₂-treated surface layer/3D perovskite/PEDOT:PSS/ITO/glass device under varying compliance currents: (a) 10⁻⁶ A, (b) 10⁻⁵ A, (c) 10⁻⁴ A, and (d) 10⁻³ A. Each state was measured for 10 consecutive cycles at a scan rate of 10 V/s with applied voltage of ±2 V.

2.3 | Operating Mechanism of Ionic Interface-Controlled HP Memory

To identify the mobile ionic species driving the resistive switching in the BDAI₂-treated devices, we first investigated the role of the top electrode. Understanding electrode dependence is critical because top electrode materials can heavily dictate the diverse resistive switching behaviors in halide perovskite memories [55]. Halide perovskite memristors generally operate via either electrochemical metallization (ECM) from active metal electrodes (e.g., Ag, Cu) or valence change mechanism (VCM) driven by intrinsic halide ions/vacancies. Therefore, it is crucial to explicitly rule out the interference of Ag migration to identify ion migration species.

While our observations of non-filamentary switching already strongly contradict ECM behavior, we fabricated identical devices using an inert Au top electrode for definitive proof. As shown in Figure 6, the Au-electrode devices exhibited the exact same gradual, analog, and multi-level switching characteristics as the Ag-based devices. To activate the dual-inductive resistive switching, the Au-electrode devices required a slightly increased applied voltage sweep of ±2 V [55–57]. This higher driving voltage might be physically attributed to the larger work function and chemical inertness of Au for initial halide ion accumulation. Notably, just like the Ag reference devices, these Au devices also showed a clear transition to non-zero crossing behavior at higher compliance

currents. Since Au is highly resistant to electrochemical oxidation and migration, this result clearly confirms that the core switching mechanism is not dominated by active metal penetration and is strictly embedded in the perovskite layer. With Ag filament formation clearly excluded, we further investigated the intrinsic conduction mechanism.

At the microscopic level, the complete suppression of stochastic filamentary pathways is achieved through a synergetic combination of chemical defect passivation and physical steric hindrance. As physically supported by the morphology analysis (Figure 1; Figure S2) and related literatures [58, 59], the BDAI₂ treatment effectively penetrates and passivates the surface and underlying grain boundaries of the perovskite. The amine groups of the diammonium efficiently coordinate with unsaturated Pb ions and iodine vacancies. This passivation heals the defect sites and fundamentally inhibits the highly localized aggregation of halide vacancies, which are the primary precursors for filament formation. Simultaneously, the inherent structural bulkiness of the BDA²⁺ cation provides a significant steric hindrance effect. This spatial barrier restricts the abrupt, uncontrolled ionic transport of halide ions. Instead of forming stochastic localized pathways, these combined effects force the mobile halide ions to distribute uniformly, allowing the BDAI₂ layer to act as a stable ion reservoir for the delocalized, quantitative modulation of the interfacial barrier.

FIGURE 7 | Conduction mechanism analysis of the Ag/BDAI₂/HP/PEDOT:PSS/ITO device. Double-logarithmic I-V plots at HRS and LRS for (a,b) the initial first sweeps and (c,d) subsequent stable switching curves. All measurements were performed at a scan rate of 10V/s with a compliance current of 10⁻⁵ A.

To provide direct macroscopic evidence of this non-filamentary resistive behavior, we conducted area-dependent I-V characteristics using the Au-electrode devices with varying cell diameters of 200 and 400 μm (Figure S7). In typical filamentary switching memristors, the low-resistance state (LRS) resistance is strictly independent of the electrode area due to the localized nature of the conductive pathway. In contrast, the BDAI₂-treated memristor here exhibits a clear area-dependent current scaling, where the current magnitude increases proportionally with the larger cell area, which definitely means interface-type switching [60, 61]. It explicitly proves that the intrinsic conduction due to halide ions/vacancies occurs uniformly across the entire modulated interface layer rather than through localized stochastic filaments.

Subsequently, to elucidate the conduction mechanisms in the stably programmable BDAI₂-treated memristor, the I-V characteristics were plotted on a double-logarithmic plot ($\ln I$ - $\ln V$) and analyzed using the relation of $I \propto V^\alpha$ [24, 62, 63], as shown in Figure 7, with the corresponding conceptual schematic processes illustrated in Figure S8. Figure 7a,b displays the initial switching curves of the device under positive bias and negative bias, respectively. The device shows forming-free characteristics, where the RS occurs at a low operating voltage without requiring a high-voltage electroforming process typically observed in most HP memristors for stable repeatability. Rather than complete suppression of ion migration, this suggests that the quasi-2D/3D

heterostructure induced by the BDAI₂ passivation establishes a highly uniform, low-activation energy pathway for halide ions at the interface. This facilitates non-filamentary, uniform ionic accumulation and dynamic interfacial barrier modulation without triggering irreversible localized bulk breakdown.

Furthermore, the introduction of the diammonium iodide (BDAI₂) as an additional discrete interfacial layer uniquely enables dual-inductive switching behavior, where the SET process is successfully triggered under both positive and negative voltage bias sweeps. Regarding the representative conduction fitting, unlike typical memristive devices that show ideal Ohmic behavior ($\alpha \approx 1$) in the low-voltage regime, our device exhibits a continuous non-linear current growth. This indicates a barrier-modulated conduction mechanism where carrier transport is governed by shallow interfacial states rather than simple bulk resistance. In Figure 7a for the positive region at initial sweep, the current exhibits a steep dependence with a slope of 3.53 as the positive voltage increases in HRS. This pronounced non-linearity corresponds to ion-driven barrier narrowing, where the massive accumulation of mobile ions at the BDAI₂ interface dynamically reduces the effective injection barrier width. Following the SET process, the LRS shows a slope of 1.53 (>1), which notably deviates from the ideal Ohmic value. Since the formation of a physical metallic-like filament behavior would strictly dictate an ideal Ohmic conduction, this non-Ohmic LRS

behavior provides definitive evidence that the device operates via a non-filamentary mechanism. It implies that the current flow through a highly concentrated, homogeneously distributed ionic layer at the interface, rather than through a localized stochastic filament. This persistent non-linearity in the LRS is a hallmark of non-equilibrium ion dynamics at the BDAI₂ interface. Similarly, during the initial negative sweep in Figure 7b, the HRS demonstrates a steep slope of 3.33, while the subsequent LRS maintains a non-ideal linearity with a slope of 1.35, explicitly rejecting the formation of random conductive metallic filaments.

The stabilized switching cycles in Figure 7c,d further confirm the conduction mechanism. In these states, a clear transition in the conduction behavior is observed as the dynamic halide reservoir of the BDAI₂ layer optimizes the ion distribution for uniform, non-filamentary switching. Under positive sweep, the HRS slope reaches 2.50, and the LRS slope maintained at 1.40. The reduction in the HRS transition slope (from 3.53 to 2.50) physically validates that the interfacial states have been effectively stabilized, requiring a lower external field to achieve the necessary barrier modulation. At the negative bias sweep, the HRS slope shows a steep value of 2.72, and the LRS slope reaches 1.09, near-linear yet distinct from purely metallic behavior. This continuous bidirectional ionic modulation by the BDAI₂ interface layer successfully consolidates a highly robust, delocalized high-conductance state at the interface, strictly maintaining the non-filamentary structural integrity [8, 24]. This ion-mediated interfacial reconfiguration not only governs the dual-inductive switching in both polarities but also provides a fundamental origin for the programmable non-zero crossing characteristics [3], fundamentally distinguishing our devices from conventional memristors (see Table S2 for a comprehensive performance comparison).

3 | Conclusions

In summary, we successfully demonstrated a highly stable, forming-free halide perovskite memristor by engineering the interface between metal and HP via BDAI₂ interfacial treatment. Comprehensive structural, optical, and chemical characterization, including SEM, AFM, XRD, PL, and XPS, confirmed that the diammonium BDAI₂ treatment effectively passivated interfacial defects, forming a uniform cross-linked ion-blocking network in the halide perovskite layer without degrading the underlying 3D bulk morphology.

Benefiting from this optimized ionic interface, the device exhibits remarkably reproducible dual-inductive resistive switching and programmable multi-level states, tightly controlled by the compliance current and scan speed. Through rigorous conduction mechanism analysis, we elucidated that the resistive switching dynamics are governed by a purely non-filamentary mechanism, rather than destructive, randomly localized filament formation. Specifically, the BDAI₂ layer acts as a rigid ion-blocking barrier, resulting in asymmetric delocalized accumulation of mobile halide ions at the interface, which dynamically modulates the energy barriers. Furthermore, the prominent non-zero crossing behavior under high current injection further corroborates this mechanism. This hysteresis characteristics provide fundamental insights into novel ion-electronic phenomena in halide

perovskites. The massive amounts and relaxation time of interfacial ion accumulation temporarily sustains the lowered energy barrier, generating a residual conduction current at zero bias.

Ultimately, this interfacial defect-engineered, non-filamentary approach effectively suppresses irreversible structural degradation over extended continuous operations (4000 cycles). This study provides a highly reliable and spatiotemporally programmable switching paradigm for new multifunctional memristive and advanced reconfigurable neuromorphic computing architectures.

4 | Experimental Section

4.1 | Materials for Dual Inductive HP-Based Memristor

Formamidinium iodide (FAI, >99.99%, Greatcellsolar), methylammonium bromide (MABr, >99.99%, Greatcellsolar), cesium Iodide (CsI, 99.9%, Thermo Scientific Chemicals), lead iodide (PbI₂, 99.99%, trace metals basis, TCI), lead bromide (PbBr₂, >98.0%, TCI), butane-1,4-diammonium iodide (BDAI₂, Greatcellsolar), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, anhydrous ≥99.8%, Avantorsciences), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, ≥99.7%, Sigma-Aldrich), poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene)-poly(styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT: PSS, Heraeus Clevis P VP AI 4083), 2-propanol (IPA, Scharlau) and chlorobenzene (anhydrous, 99.8%, Sigma-Aldrich) were purchased and used with no further purification.

4.2 | Preparation of the Precursor Solution Based on HP

1.0 M of FAI, 0.2 M of MABr, 0.063 M of CsI, 1.1 M of PbI₂, and 0.2 M of PbBr₂ were completely mixed in DMF: DMSO (v/v%, 4:1) solvent with a magnetic stirrer for perovskite layer composed of Cs_{0.05}(FA_{0.83}MA_{0.17})_{0.95}Pb(I_{0.83}Br_{0.13})₃. BDAI₂ was dissolved in IPA solvent with 4 mg/mL of concentration.

4.3 | Fabrication of the Memristor Device

Indium tin oxide (ITO)-coated glass substrates with 1.5 cm × 2.0 cm were sequentially cleaned by ultrasonication in detergent with deionized water, acetone, and isopropanol for 15 min each. The cleaned ITO substrates were ultraviolet-ozone (UVO)-treated for 30 min. A PEDOT: PSS solution was filtered through a 0.45 μm PTFE-H syringe filter and deposited onto the substrates, spin-coated with 4000 rpm for 30 s, and annealed at 150°C for 10 min on a hot plate. Prior to the HP layer deposition onto PEDOT: PSS-coated ITO substrates, the HP precursor solution was filtered using a PTFE-H syringe filter with a pore size of 0.22 μm. The filtered HP precursor of 30 μL was dropped onto ITO substrates and spin-coated through two-steps of 1000 rpm for 10 s and 4000 rpm for 30 s. During the spin-coating step, 0.2 mL of chlorobenzene was dropped onto the wet film. The as-spun film was then annealed at 150°C for 10 min on a hot plate. Following annealing, the substrates were cooled to room temperature before post-treatment. The BDAI₂ solution was

dynamically dripped onto the HP films for post-treatment. The films were subsequently annealed at 70°C for 5 min. Finally, a 100 nm-thick top electrode was deposited onto the treated films by thermal evaporation. A dot-shaped shadow mask with variable diameters of 100, 200, and 400 μm was employed.

4.4 | Characterizations

X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were performed using a CUBIX DY0822 X-ray diffractometer (PANalytical Ltd.) equipped with Cu K α radiation (wavelength = 1.54056 Å). The diffraction data were collected over a 2 θ range of 5°–60° with a step scan size of 0.02°. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) data was acquired using a SPECS spectrometer (PHOIBOS 150 MCD-9 detector) and a 200 W non-monochromatic Al K α radiation source with a pass energy of 30 eV, utilizing CASA software for spectral deconvolution. Surface and cross-sectional morphologies were examined using a field emission scanning electron microscope (HRFESEM, GeminiSEM 500, ZEISS). Surface topography and roughness were analyzed by atomic force microscope (AFM, Multimode 8, BRUKER) operated in tapping mode with OTESPA-R3 tip. Steady-state photoluminescence (PL) spectra were acquired using an Edinburgh Instruments (FLS1100 spectrofluorometer) with a 450 W Xenon lamp light. The system utilized double monochromators for both excitation and emission, with a silicon detector for signal acquisition. Electrical characteristics were measured using a KEYSIGHT B1500A semiconductor parameter analyzer integrated with a probe station under ambient air conditions at room temperature, without any device encapsulation.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18800276>, reference number 10.5281/zenodo.18800276.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting File: adfm75888-sup-0001-SuppMat.docx.